

THE EFFECT OF CREDITWORTHINESS ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE SUSTAINABLE GROWTH RATE AND THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF BANKS - AN APPLIED RESEARCH ON ASHUR INTERNATIONAL BANK.

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Summary:

The study aimed to identify the effect of creditworthiness on the relationship between sustainable growth rate and financial performance in a sample of Iraqi commercial banks. The researcher used the descriptive analytical approach, and used data analysis for five Iraqi commercial banks. The most important results of the study were as follows: The results of the study indicated that there is an effect of creditworthiness on the rate of sustainable growth and financial performance in three banks from the study sample, and there is no effect of creditworthiness in two banks, The study recommended, seeking to determine the appropriate creditworthiness ratio, which achieves the best sustainable growth rate and financial performance for banks.

Key words: Creditworthiness, Sustainable Growth Rate, Financial Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

In emerging countries like Iraq, the banking sector is still the backbone of the state economy, with the banking industry nowadays, especially in Iraq, facing a direct challenge, apart from the emergence of new competitors such as capital markets, money markets, etc. - Banking financial institutions, the competition in the Iraqi banking industry itself shows a significant escalation, which obligated the banking sector to pay great attention to the sustainable growth rate first, and it means the maximum growth rate that a financial company or a bank can maintain without it. The need to finance growth with additional equity or debt. Growth rate includes maximizing sales and revenue without increasing leverage. Achieving a growth rate can help banks avoid over-indebtedness and financial distress. For the bank to operate above its growth rate, it will need to maximize sales efforts and focus on higher margin products and services. Also, inventory management is important and management must have an understanding of the ongoing inventory needed to match and maintain the company's sales level. As an aid in determining whether it is managing day-to-day operations properly, including paying its bills and getting payments on time, accounts payable management needs timely management to keep cash flow running smoothly. and secondly; Creditworthiness is how a lender decides that you will default on your debt obligations, or your entitlement to new

credit, creditworthiness is what creditors look at before agreeing to any new credit for you, creditworthiness is determined by several factors including Your payment history and credit score. Some lending institutions also consider your available assets and the number of liabilities you have when determining the probability of default. Third, banks' financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a bank is able to use assets from its core business pattern and generate revenue. The term is also used as a general measure of a company's overall financial health over a given period. Analysts and investors use financial performance to compare similar institutions in the same industry or to compare industries or sectors in general, because the main function of a bank is to accept deposits from customers and reuse them in granting credit and the rest of the financial sector. operations, and these deposits should be better used in order to improve financial performance, which will positively reflect on the market value of the bank. Therefore, this study came to link between sustainable growth and creditworthiness and its impact on the financial performance of Iraqi commercial banks. The problem of the study is the following question: What is the impact of creditworthiness on the rate of sustainable growth and financial performance in Ashur International Bank?

The study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- Determining the impact of creditworthiness on the sustainable growth rate and financial performance of the bank.
- Presenting the creditworthiness of the banks during the study period, and determining its impact on the sustainable growth rate and financial performance
- A statement of the differences in the impact of the creditworthiness of each individual on the rate of sustainable growth and the financial performance of the bank.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1) Concept Of Creditworthiness

The concept of creditworthiness or credit rating is a difficult concept for the ordinary reader, or non-specialist, although its meaning is in circulation almost daily for borrowers from banks and financial institutions, and it is interested in reaching a conclusion that granting credit without conducting a study of the merit of the customers who are supposed to be granted loans, It is something that may result in facing the risk of future default in the payment of credit.

(Synek, 2010) defines creditworthiness as follows: "Creditworthiness is the ability of a company to increase its invested capital, achieve impact and meet all obligations; it is usually evaluated according to the company's financial position, technical and business reputation and expected income status. This is ascertained by By banks prior to granting a loan or by future business partners (at chambers of commerce, banks or specialized information offices (Synek, 2010) The economic encyclopedia has defined creditworthiness as the ability to meet obligations correctly ... It includes the solvency and level of business activities of the entity.

(Estrella, 2000) indicated that creditworthiness refers to the financial suitability of the borrower and the extent of its ability to meet its financial obligations to others, and the concept of

creditworthiness refers to the ability of the borrower to fulfill its obligations in the face of lenders or the risk of non-payment of lenders (bond issuers) to meet its obligations represented (the value of the loan and its interests) to borrowers (holders of government securities, especially bonds) (Abdel-Aal, 2003).

There is also another definition that confirms that the merit is the evaluation carried out by the lender before approving the lending transaction. During the evaluation process, it is determined whether the borrower may default on the obligation to pay his debts in the future or not. Through this process, several factors are considered, such as the date of Payment and credit score. The amount of available assets and the amount of liabilities are also taken into consideration to determine whether or not the customer is likely to default. Furthermore, the creditworthiness of an individual or organization is determined by many companies that have established credit rating systems (vapAdmin, 2019)

When assessing creditworthiness, the following points should be taken into account:

- Past payment sentiment (eg control debtors registry, insolvency registry, etc.).
- The current status of obligations to various creditors (eg, control over financial statements or pledges on real estate in the Land Registry).
- Financial status (mostly by looking at the financial statements).

Lenders assess a borrower's creditworthiness or eligibility for new credit when applying for a debt commitment, such as a personal loan, credit card, or line of credit, usually, lenders extend credit only to those they consider creditworthy, the worthy borrower a fiduciary is someone who is able and responsible enough to repay their debts in a timely manner. If the lender thinks you are a risky borrower, you are unlikely to qualify for new credit (Lindsay VanSomeren & Jordan Tarver, 2021) Creditworthiness is the way a lender decides that you will default on your debt obligations, or your entitlement to receive new credit, your creditworthiness is what creditors look at before agreeing to any new credit for you, creditworthiness is determined by several factors including your payment history and credit score. Some lending institutions also take into account the available assets and the number of liabilities you have when determining the probability of default (RAJEEV DHIR & THOMAS BROCK, 2021).

We conclude from the above that:

- Creditworthiness is the way a lender will know if a borrower will default on your debt obligations.
- Creditworthiness is determined by several factors including payment history and credit score.
- Improving or maintaining creditworthiness is as simple as making payments on time.
- Creditworthiness is a term that gets thrown around a lot in the financial world, and you should understand what it means because it plays a major role in many financial decisions.

2) Concept Of Sustainable Growth

The sustainable growth rate is the financing of capital by maintaining the ratio between capital and debt (Septianingsih, 2013). Meanwhile, according to Saputro, (2013), the sustainable growth rate is the maximum level at which a company can increase sales without running out of financial resources. Moreover, Lockwood & Prombutr, 2010 stated that the sustainable growth rate is a multiple measure. The facets can be broken down into separate components that reflect the company's retention policy (retention rate), affordability (net profit margin), asset efficiency (asset turnover), and financing strategy (leverage), all of which are key determinants of performance (Marwa & Aziakpono, 2015). The main reason a sustainable growth rate is so beneficial is because it can combine the operational elements (profit margin and asset efficiency) and financial elements (capital structure and retention rate) into one comprehensive measure (Amouzesh, et al., 2011).

According to Devie, (2003), a company's growth in financial management is measured based on changes in sales, even in financial terms how much growth should be (sustainable growth rate) by looking at the alignment of investment and financing decisions. The growth of the company will have consequences for the increased investment in the assets of the company and will eventually require the provision of funds to purchase the assets, in other words, the growth of the company has consequences for investment decisions and financing decisions (Hassan and Gabr, 2016). According to Ratnawati, (2007), a company's sustainable growth is the rate at which a company's sales can grow depending on how assets are supported to increase sales. In addition to the level of sales, company growth can also be measured by asset growth or by investment opportunities as with different combinations of investment opportunity group values.

The sustainable growth rate (SGR) is the maximum rate of growth that a company or social enterprise can sustain without having to fund growth with additional equity or debt. SGR involves maximizing sales and revenue without increasing leverage. Achieving SGR can help a company avoid excessive leverage and financial hardship (Hassan and Jabr, 2016)

The sustainable growth rate is the rate of growth that a company can expect in the long run. Often referred to as G, the sustainable growth rate can be calculated by multiplying the company's earnings retention rate by its return on equity. The growth rate can be calculated on a historical and average basis in order to determine the average growth rate of the company since its inception (Marwa & Aziakpono, 2015). The sustainable growth rate is an indication of the stage a company is in, during its life cycle. It is important to understand where a company is in its life cycle. The situation often defines corporate finance objectives, such as the funding sources to use, dividend policies, and the overall competitive strategy (Al-Zubaidi et al., 2019).

The growth ratio can also be used by creditors to determine the probability of a company defaulting on its loans. A high growth rate may indicate that the company is focusing on investing in positive R&D and NPV projects, which may delay debt repayment. A company with a high growth rate is generally considered to be more risky, as it is likely to experience greater volatility in earnings from one period to the next (El-Feki, 2019).

Tildikov (2009) developed a systematic model of sustainable growth as shown in the figure below. Abbreviations were used for visual ease. Return on equity is the return on equity, ROA means return on assets, EBIT is the abbreviation for earnings before interest and taxes, and T is the abbreviation for tax.

Figure No (1): Sustainable growth rate according to (Tildikov, 2009)

From the previous figure, the sustainable growth rate can be calculated by applying the following equation:

$$\text{SGR} = \text{ROE} \times \text{Retention Ratio}$$

A sustainable growth rate is made up of different components. Shown in the previous figure, there are seven key indicators needed to calculate SGR: earnings before interest and taxes, revenue, assets, equity, taxes, interest rate, and dividends.

The researcher sees the sustainable growth rate (SGR) as the maximum growth rate of a company in sales using internal financial resources, with no need to increase debt or issue new shares, logically speaking, the sustainable growth rate is the rate at which profits and profits of any company can continue to grow indefinitely. The implicit assumption behind the sustainable growth rate is that no new debt or equity has been issued and that the company's capital structure has not changed.

3) Concept of Financial Performance

There is an importance for the financial performance of banking institutions, as a result of the role of these institutions in their work as a financial intermediary that works to transfer funds from the owners of the surplus to the owners of the financial deficit in the form of investments and credit financing, in addition to the large amount of funds dealt with and the speed of their turnover, and to ensure the continuity of this process, it is necessary to maintain Good financial performance for these banking institutions, so a process of measuring the financial performance of these institutions must be carried out on an ongoing basis, based on scientific standards and foundations that show the financial performance and the actual results of them. Achieving

better effectiveness to reach the financial goals to be achieved, and these institutions seek to achieve many goals, including: the institution's reputation, financial goals, effectiveness and efficiency in the exploitation of resources, and the development of decision-making processes (Al-Masry, 2005 (Al-Saati, 2018). The financial performance represents the company's ability to achieve its financial goals, and it is the main pillar in supporting the various businesses that the company engages in. It expresses the company's financial performance through financial indicators such as profitability, liquidity, and others (Al-Khatib, 2010). He also defined it (Daden and Hafsi, 2014), as "the role that institutional processes and activities contribute to providing an addition or value resulting from the use of available human and financial resources, and this value is measured through effectiveness in performance, represented by working to achieve goals at the lowest possible costs." "

Financial performance is defined as the extent to which the activities carried out by companies contribute to creating value or efficiency in the use of available financial resources by achieving financial goals at the lowest costs (Abdel-Wahab, 2014). Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a company uses assets from its core business and revenue generation. The term is also used as a general measure of a company's overall financial health over a given period. Analysts and investors use financial performance to compare similar companies in the same industry or to compare industries or sectors in aggregate ((Will KENTON et al., 2021.

There are many stakeholders in a company, including trade creditors, bondholders, investors, employees, and management. Each group has its own interest in tracking the company's financial performance. Financial performance determines how successful a company is in generating revenue, managing its assets and liabilities, and the financial interests of stakeholders and shareholders. There are many ways to measure financial performance, but all measures must be taken in aggregate. Items, such as revenue from operations, operating income, or cash flow from operations, can be used in addition to total unit sales. Furthermore, an analyst or investor may want to take a deeper look at the financial statements and look for margin growth rates or any declining debt. Six Sigma methods focus on this aspect. The researcher believes that financial performance is the ability of business organizations, including banks, to reduce their costs and increase revenues, in order to fulfill their obligations towards others, and at the same time determine the extent of optimal utilization of resources.

We conclude from the above that the financial performance means:

- Financial performance tells investors about the company's general well-being. It's a snapshot of the economic health and function of its management.
- The financial statements used in evaluating overall financial performance include the balance sheet, income statement and cash flow statement.
- Financial performance indicators are quantifiable measures used to measure how well a company is performing.
- No single measure should be used to determine a company's financial performance.

3. SPECIFICATIONS OF THE EXPERIMENTAL MODEL AND ESTIMATION METHODS

The study model and its procedures are considered a major axis through the implementation of the applied aspect of the study, and thus achieving the objectives that the study seeks to achieve, and with the aim of designing a quantitative model for the matrix of independent variables that are represented in the creditworthiness of the study sample banks which are (5), and a model was built, concerned With the effect of that matrix of variables in (net assets turnover, profit distribution, profit margin, liquidity, leverage, stock return, stock price, cash flow), the statistical analysis program E-Views has been used in data analysis, which is one of the latest programs in the analysis This program can be used through the econometrics methodology according to the following stages:

1. Stage of Determining the Mathematical Form of the Model:

The mathematical form of the model means the number of equations it contains (the model may be linear or non-linear) and the degree of homogeneity of each equation (it may be homogeneous or heterogeneous of a certain degree). Even to some extent in determining some of the features of the appropriate mathematical form.

1. The mathematical form of the sustainable growth variables for this study can be determined as follows:

$$CR = F(NAT, PM, DD)$$

$$CR = B_0 + B_1 NAT + B_2 PM + B_3 DD + 4$$

Third: Signs of landmarks according to economic theory.

B_0 = Static signal.

B_1 = Signal of the net asset turnover coefficient (positive).

B_2 = Signal of the profit margin factor (positive).

B_3 = Signal of the profit distribution coefficient (positive).

- 2) The mathematical form of the financial performance variables for this study is as follows:

$$CR = F(LI, FLE, CF, SD, SP)$$

$$CR = B_0 + B_1 LI + B_2 FLE + B_3 CF + B_4 SD + B_5 SP + 4$$

B_0 = Static signal.

B_1 = Liquidity coefficient sign (positive).

B_2 = leverage coefficient signal (positive).

B_3 = cash flow coefficient sign (positive).

B_4 = Equity Coefficient of Return (Positive) signal.

B_5 = Signal of the stock price coefficient (positive).

2. Model Ashur International Bank: The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method will be used to estimate the model.

- The time series stability test: On the applied level, there are tests that can be used to test the stability of the time series, the most important of which is the extended Dickey Fuller test.

Table (1): Expanded Dickey-Fuller Test Results (Time-Series Stability, Level 1 and Differences)

Variable stability level	Variables	Significance level 5%	Variables
The second difference	-3,9788	-3,6948	NAT
unstable	-2,3314	-3,6948	PM
unstable	-2,29644	-3,6948	DD
unstable	-2,5117	-3,6948	LI
The second difference	-4,15593	-3,6948	FLE
The second difference	-4,7778	-3,5195	CF
unstable	-3,6802	-3,6948	SD
The second difference	-5,9195	-3,5195	SP

The results of the expanded Dickey-Fuller tests indicated that the study variables (NAT, FLE, CF, SP) are stable in the second difference at the level of significance 5%, while variables (PM, DD, LI, SD) are unstable at the three levels.

3. The stages of estimating and evaluating the model:

Estimating the standard model is an attempt to reach acceptable estimates for the values of transactions, and the estimation process takes place after collecting data, as it is the process of transforming the functional relationship into a mathematical relationship, and then estimating the values of transactions using one of the econometric methods. The estimated model can be clarified as follows :

Table No (2): Estimated model for the impact of creditworthiness on the sustainable growth rate

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
C	16,432	13,2316	1,2418	0,2693
DD	11,2485	4,299011	2,61654	0,0473
NAT	-1,06632	1,7141	-0,62208	0,5612
PM	1,6389	1,56131	1,0497	0,3419
R²=81%		D-W=1,18	F-Statistic=0,02	

Through the results of the above table, the estimated model can be written as follows:

$$CR=16,432+11,2485DD$$

$$(1,241) (2,616)$$

The results of the model, which indicated the significance of the study variable, the distribution of profits (DD), where the value of Prob was (0.04), as well as the absence of self-correlation,

as the tests of examining the model gave good indicators and results, as they indicated that the increase in creditworthiness led to an increase in creditworthiness. Distribution of profits at Ashur International Bank and there was no effect of creditworthiness on net asset turnover (NAT) and profit margin (PM) from this period. We also note that the effect of creditworthiness on dividend distribution amounted to 82% where (F) equals (0.02) Evidence of high morale.

Figure (2): The graph of the estimated model

After obtaining the estimated values, there are three basic sets of criteria that are considered as the basis for the estimation process:

- **Economic criterion:** The economic criterion relates to the scope of the results with the assumptions of economic theory. Through this, the type of coefficient relationship is ascertained. If the relationship matches the size and direction of the economic theory, then the meaning of this model, after excluding the variables that do not have a significant effect, came the indication of the profit distribution coefficient. (Positive) to agree to the operative theory of economics.
- **Statistical Standard:** This is shown through:
 - The ability of the model to explain the phenomenon under study.
 - Confidence rate in the model parameters estimates using the coefficient of determination, and this can be clarified through the following table:

Table (3): Form fit quality test

Variable	Adjust R ²
CR,DD	70%

From the results of the above table, we note that the value of the coefficient of determination is equal to 70% until the dependent variable is explained by 70% of the variables that occurred from the independent variable

• **T-Test**

The T-Test is used to test the effect of each variable on the other, in which the probability value of (T) is compared with a level of significance (5%). In other words, it is not statistically reliable. This can be illustrated by the following table:

Table (4): T-Test test of creditworthiness model variables on sustainable growth

Variable	Coefficient	Test Statistic	Prob
C	16,4324	13,2316	0,2693
DD	11,2485	4,299011	0,047

The results of the above table confirmed the significance of T parameter to reject the null hypothesis.

- **Standard Standard:** Include;

The problem of linear correlation: This can be clarified through the following table:

Table No (5): Matrix of correlation between variables

	CR	DD	NAT	PM
CR	1,000000	0,881406	-0,185999	0,645023
DD	0,881406	1,000000	-0,186650	0,581353
NAT	-0,185999	-0,186650	1,000000	0,289598
PM	0,645023	0,581353	0,289598	1,000000

From the results of the above table it is clear that there is no linear correlation between the variables.

- **The problem of autocorrelation:** the value of (D-W) is (1.18), and this value indicates that there is no autocorrelation problem.

The problem of variance difference: This can be clarified through the following table:

Table No (6): A test to detect the variance difference problem

F-statistic 0,08	Prob 0,77
Obs squared 0,11	Prob 0,73

We note from the results of the above table that the credit value of R2 reached 0.73, which is greater than (5%) to accept the null hypothesis that there is no variance problem.

Table No (7): Estimated model for the impact of creditworthiness on financial performance

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
C	40,5355	26,83538	1,510526	0,2281
CF	0,70133	0,12264	5,718416	0,0106
FLE	1,39255	1,36514	1,020076	0,38823
LI	-0,1366	0,067742	-2,001740	0,1370
SD	3,3629	31,56034	0,106555	0,9219
SP	-31,34213	15,14386	-2,069626	0,1303
R²=95%		D-W=2,6		F-Statistic=0,03

Through the results of the above table, the estimated model can be written as follows:

$$CR=40,5355+0,70133CF$$

(1,510) (5, 7184)

The results of the above table show the significance of the study variable, cash flow (CF), which has a value (Prob) of the variable (0.01), as the model examination tests gave good indicators and results, as they indicated that the increase in creditworthiness led to an increase in cash flow (CF). At Ashur International Bank, there was no effect of creditworthiness on the rest of the financial performance variables of the bank. We also note the overall significance of the model. This is shown by the F-statistic value, which amounted to (0, 03).

Figure No (3): Graphic representation of the model

The chart also justifies the effect of creditworthiness on cash flow.

- Evaluation of the estimated model.

First: The economic criterion: In this model, the cash flow coefficient signal was in agreement with the utterance of the economic theory.

- **The statistical standard:** This can be clarified through the following table:

Table (8): Form fit quality test

Variable	Adjust R ²
CR,CF	86%

From the results of the above table, the value of the coefficient of determination R² equals 86% to the independent variable, it is explained by 86% of the changes that occurred from the dependent variable.

- **T-Test:** This can be clarified through the following table:

Table (9): T-Test for creditworthiness model variables on financial performance

Variable	Coefficient	Test Statistic	Prob
C	40,5355	1,510526	0,2281
CF	0,70133	5,7184	0,010

We notice from the results of the above table that the T parameter of the variable (CF) is significant, which amounted to (0,010) to reject the null hypothesis.

- **The Standard Model:** It includes;

The problem of linear correlation: This can be clarified through the following table:

Table (10): Matrix of correlation between variables

	CR	CF	FLE	LI	SD	SP
CR	1,000000	0,911303	0,409902	-0,002966	-0,436227	-0,221306
CF	0,911303	1,000000	0,346292	0,133458	-0,332004	-0,113637
FLE	0,409902	0,345292	1,000000	0,392996	0,015675	-0,341930
LI	-0,002966	0,133458	0,392996	1,000000	0,486220	-0,709365
SD	-0,436227	-0,332004	0,015675	0,486220	1,000000	-0,166063
SP	-0,221306	-0,113637	-0,341930	-0,709365	-0,166063	1,000000

From the results of the above table it is clear that there is no linear correlation between the variables.

- The problem of autocorrelation: the value of (D-W) is (2.6), and this value indicates that there is no autocorrelation.
- The problem of variance difference: This can be clarified through the following table:

Table No (11): Tests to detect asymmetry problem

F-statistic 0,006	Prob 0,94
Obs squared 0,0080	Prob 0,92

We note from the results of the above table that the probability value (R2) amounted to 0.95 which is greater than (0.05) to accept the null hypothesis that there is no variance problem.

CONCLUSION

The results of the first model that tests the effect between creditworthiness on the sustainable growth rate in Ashur Bank reached to the significance of the study's profit distribution variable (DD), where the value of Prob was (0.04), as well as the absence of autocorrelation, as the model examination tests gave Good indicators and results, as they indicated that the increase in creditworthiness led to an increase in the distribution of profits in Ashur International Bank, and there was no effect of creditworthiness on the net asset turnover (NAT) and the profit margin (PM) from this period. We also note that the effect of creditworthiness on the distribution of profits It reached 82%, where (F) equals (0.02) evidence of high morale.

Resources

1. SYNEK, Miloslav(2010). KISLINGEROVÁ, Eva. a kol. Podniková ekonomika. 5. přeprac. a dopl. vydání, Praha: C. H. Beck, 498 s., ISBN 978-80-7400-336-3.
2. Edwards, B. 2004. Credit Management Handbook. Hants: Gower Publishing Limited.
3. vapAdmin (2019): What is creditworthiness, <https://www.vapulus.com/ar/>.
4. Ahmed Al-Masry (2005): Department of Commercial and Islamic Banks, (Dr. I) Alexandria: University Youth Foundation.

5. Asia Al-Wafi, Qenat Al-Taher (2021): The specificity of the Islamic economy in the field of bank credit, *Journal of Economic Studies and Research in Renewable Energies*, Volume 8, No. 2, Algeria.
6. Al-Khatib, Muhammad Mahmoud (2010): Financial performance and its impact on the shares of joint stock companies, Amman, Al-Manhal Publishing.
7. Khatib, Manal (2014) The cost of bank credit and its risk measurement by application to a Syrian commercial bank. Unpublished Master's Thesis, University of Aleppo, Syria.
8. Daden, Abdel-Wahab, and Hafsi Rachid (2014) Analysis of the financial performance of Algerian small and medium-sized enterprises using the method of discriminatory factor analysis during the period between 2006-2011 *Oasis Journal of Research*, University of Ghardaia, 7(2)22-34.
9. Al-Daghim, Abdel Aziz. (2006): Credit analysis and its role in rationalizing bank lending operations. *Tishreen University Journal of Scientific Studies and Research*, 28(3), 208-191.
10. Rasha Ali Ibrahim El-Feki, (2019): Reflections between the relationship of ownership structure and the level of disclosure of future information, an applied study on real estate investment companies in the Egyptian Stock Exchange, Faculty of Commerce, Suez Canal University.
11. Al-Zubaidi, Haider Mahmoud Ali, and others, (2019): The role of value-based management in sustainable growth, an applied study in a sample of companies listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange, *The Scientific Journal of Economics and Business*, Volume 3, Issue 6.
12. Sajid Khaled Muhammad Deeb Abdel-Daem (2019): The reality of intellectual capital and its impact on the financial performance of the banks listed on the Palestine Stock Exchange, Master's thesis, College of Commerce, Islamic University, Gaza-Palestine.
13. Shatha Abdul-Hussein Jabr and Anwar Mustafa Hassan, (2016): Analysis of expected profits within the framework of the relationship between sustainable growth and actual growth, *Journal of Accounting and Financial Studies*, Vol. 11, No. 36.
14. Dia Ahmed Al-Saati, (2018): The Impact of Deposits and Credit Facilities on the Financial Performance of Banks in the Palestine Exchange, Master Thesis, Islamic University of Gaza, College of Commerce, Palestine.
15. Tarek Abdel-Aal Hammad (2003): "International developments and their implications for the work of banks", University Publishing House, Egypt.
16. Abdel Hamid Mohamed Al Shawarby, Mohamed Abdel Hamid Al Shawarby (2002): Credit Risk Management from the Banking and Legal Perspectives, Mansha'at Al Maaref, Alexandria, Egypt.
17. Abdel-Wahab Daden, Shabeer Khafji (2014) Analyzing the financial performance of Algerian small and medium-sized enterprises using the method of analysis during 2006-2011, *Al-Wahat Journal for Research and Studies*, 2 (7).
18. Lama Muhammad Mansour, Shatha Abdul-Hussein Jabr, Muhammad Ali Musa, (2021): The impact of sustainable growth in the value of companies, an applied study of the industrial sector companies listed in the Iraqi stock market, *Journal of Financial and Accounting Sciences*, Volume 1, Issue 2, the Iraqi Ministry of Finance .
19. Muhammad Ahmad Khader and Fayhaa Abdullah Yaqoub, (2021): Standards of creditworthiness for customers and their impact on the liquidity of private Iraqi commercial banks (applied research in a sample of private Iraqi commercial banks), *Journal of Accounting and Financial Studies*, Volume (16), Issue (46) , Iraq.
20. Muhammad Khaled Abu al-Fahm (2005), Determinants of Creditworthiness of the Palestinian Authority, a paper presented to the first scientific conference entitled (Investment and Finance in Palestine between

Development Prospects and Contemporary Challenges), held at the Faculty of Commerce at the Islamic University for the period from 8-9/5.

21. Muhammad Naim Salem Shabeer (2021): The Impact of Risk Disclosure on Financial Performance (Applied Study: on Banks Listed on the Palestine Stock Exchange), Master's Thesis, College of Commerce, Islamic University of Gaza, College of Commerce, Palestine-Gaza.
22. Muawiya Suleiman Hassan Abu Al-Qumboz (2020): The impact of income diversification on the financial performance of banks listed on the Palestine Exchange" (Applied Study), Master's Thesis, College of Commerce, Islamic University, Gaza-Palestine.
23. Naji Ahmed, (2015) The Impact of Credit Risk on the Profitability of Commercial Banks in Iraq, Tikrit Journal of Administrative and Economic Sciences, Volume 11, Issue 33.
24. Nihad Na'no' (2018): The extent of the Syrian commercial banks' commitment to the determinants of the decision to grant bank credit, a field study, Economic and Legal Sciences Series, 2079 (4) 39, 3073.
25. Helppi, M. & Paloheimo, A. 2005. Ulkomaankaupan rahoitus: riskit, maksuliikenne ja ratkaisut. Helsinki: Talentum Media Oy.
26. Ijäs, S. 2002. Luottoriskien hallinta tuloksen tekijänä, Jyväskylä, Suomen Asiakastieto Oy.
27. Maaka, Z.A., 2013. The relationship between Liquidity Risk and Financial Performance of commercial Banks in Kenya. The International Journal of Accounting Information systems. 44 (5) :22_41.
28. Marwa Nyankomo & Aziakpono Meshach(2015) Financial Sustainability Of Tanzanian Saving And Credit Cooperatives, International Journal OfSocial Economics, Vol. 42 Iss 10. Oriol Aspachs, Charles A. E. Goodhart, Dimitrios P. Tsomocos, Lea Zicchino.
29. RAJEEV DHIR & THOMAS BROCK, (2021): Creditworthiness, <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/credit-worthiness.asp>.
30. ROBIN HARTILL & THOMAS J. CATALANO, (2021) , What Is Financial Performance?, <https://www.thebalance.com/financial-performance-5193413>.
31. SYNEK, Miloslav(2010). KISLINGEROVÁ, Eva. a kol. Podniková ekonomika. 5. přeprac. a dopl. vydání, Praha: C. H. Beck, 498 s., ISBN 978-80-7400-336-3.
32. Talponen, H. 2002. Hallitse Myyntisaamiset, Vantaa, WSOY.
33. Tildikov, A. 2009. Sustainable Growth Development.
34. WILL KENTON, GORDON SCOTT, ARIEL COURAGE(2021): Financial Performance, <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/f/financialperformance.asp>